

Morphological Characteristics of Jackfruit at Pasar Manna District of South Bengkulu, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk) is a plant species with high potential to develop. This species is commonly found in home gardens and adaptive to various environmental conditions. The use of jackfruit as a table fruit, vegetable, and medicine has remained limited. This study aims to assess the genetic diversity of local jackfruit in Pasar Manna District, South Bengkulu Regency, Indonesia, based on morphological traits and soluble solids concentration. Field observations and purposive sampling were employed, and plant morphology was identified using both qualitative and quantitative data based on the descriptors published by the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI, 2000). Morphological analysis of 10 jackfruit trees from five sub-districts in Pasar Manna District revealed 35 distinct traits, highlighting both differences and similarities among genotypes. The identified accessions—Tanjung Mulia1 (TM1), Tanjung Mulia2 (TM2), Ketapang Besar1 (KB1), Ketapang Besar2 (KB2), Padang Sialang1 (PS1), Padang Sialang2 (PS2), Pasar Bawah1 (PB1), Pasar Bawah2 (PB2), Pasar Mulia1 (PM1), and Pasar Mulia2 (PM2)—exhibited variations in plant morphology. TM1, TM2, and PS1 produced fruits with spheroid and ellipsoid shapes, weighing between 5.8 kg and 8.9 kg, with sugar content ranging from 11 Brix to 17 Brix. These findings indicate significant variation in fruit, stem, and seed morphology, suggesting adaptation to the local environment. This study contributes to the advancement of enhanced jackfruit germplasm in South Bengkulu, Indonesia.

KEYWORDS: Characterization, Exploration, Genetic Diversity, Germplasm, IPGRI Descriptors.

INTRODUCTION

The jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk) is native to India and has been widely distributed across various tropical regions, including Indonesia. In Indonesia, jackfruit is highly popular and readily available in nearly all areas. This species is recognized for its high productivity, rapid growth rate, and adaptability, allowing it to thrive in both lowland and highland environments. Optimal growth conditions for jackfruit trees include an annual rainfall of 1,500–2,500 mm, a minimum temperature range of 16–21°C, and a maximum temperature of 31–31.5°C [1]. Reported that jackfruit seeds constitute approximately 8–15% of the total fruit weight and are distinguished by their aromatic and sweet cotyledons [2].

Jackfruit exhibits considerable potential for further development, as nearly all parts of the plant are utilizable [3]. However, it remains largely uncultivated on a commercial scale and is more commonly found in residential yards, particularly in rural areas [4]. The limited cultivation of jackfruit is primarily due to its seasonal production and fluctuating market demand compared to other fruit crops [5]. Additionally, research on jackfruit is relatively scarce, largely due to its complex genetic and biological characteristics. The initial step in assessing genetic diversity in jackfruit involves accurate plant identification [10]. Morphological characterization is essential for evaluating superior traits, identifying varietal similarities, and structuring jackfruit populations for conservation. [7] reported significant morphological variations in jackfruit during characterization studies, which can be attributed to the species' adaptability to diverse environmental conditions.

This study aims to provide fundamental insights into the genetic diversity of jackfruit, its superior quality traits, and the relationships or similarities among different jackfruit varieties. The variations that emerge can be significant and superior in every morphological trait of jackfruit [7]. Jackfruit has majority of genotypes have regular habits and fruit grows throughout the year [8]. Research by [10] indicated that jackfruit cultivated in community gardens in Sambas Regency, Indonesia exhibits notable morphological variations, which can be classified into three major groups. The highest similarity, with a value of 10.392, was recorded between Kuburaya 02 and Pontianak 01. The morphological study of jackfruit was conducted in residential yards using a random purposive sampling method. Identifying jackfruit morphology is expected to highlight phenotypic traits that differentiate

plant varieties. This research specifically seeks to evaluate the genetic diversity of local jackfruit populations in the Pasar Manna District, South Bengkulu, Indonesia, based on morphological characteristics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Morphological identification was carried out on 10 jackfruit trees distributed across 5 sub-districts within the Pasar Manna District, South Bengkulu Regency. These sub-districts included Tanjung Mulia, Ketapang Besar, Padang Sialang, Pasar Bawah, and Pasar Mulia. Observations primarily focused on jackfruit trees growing in Tanjung Mulia and Padang Sialang. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map of Pasar Manna District from South Bengkulu Regency, Sumatra, Indonesia

The research was conducted from July to October 2024, with an emphasis on analyzing the morphological and physiological characteristics of jackfruit stems, leaves, and fruit. The equipment used included a Global Positioning System (GPS) for determining coordinates and altitude, a digital scale, a camera, a penetrometer, a refractometer, a standard color chart, a caliper, a measuring tape, a ruler, a knife, a plastic bucket, and a digital scale.

Jackfruit diversity was assessed using 27 descriptors, leading to the identification of 28 distinct jackfruit genotypes [11]. The field genetic codes indicate the origin of each identified accession, with the following abbreviations: Tanjung Mulia 1 (TM1), Tanjung Mulia 2 (TM2), Ketapang Besar 1 (KB1), Ketapang Besar 2 (KB2), Padang Sialang 1 (PS1), Padang Sialang 2 (PS2), Pasar Bawah 1 (PB1), Pasar Bawah 2 (PB2), Pasar Mulia 1 (PM1), and Pasar Mulia 2 (PM2).

The morphological characterization of jackfruit was conducted following the guidelines established by the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI) in 2000. Observations encompassed both qualitative and quantitative traits. The qualitative traits assessed in this study included crown shape, branching pattern, leaf blade shape, leaf apex shape, leaf color, leaf base shape, stalk attachment to the fruit, fruit shape, flake shape, seed shape, fruit rind color, pulp flake color, and seed coat color. Meanwhile, the quantitative traits measured comprised trunk diameter (cm), leaf blade length (cm), leaf blade width (cm), fruit length (cm), fruit width (cm), fruit diameter (cm), fruit weight (kg), fruit hardness (kgf), weight fresh flake without seed (g), seed weight (g), dami weight and fruit rind per kg (g), dami weight (kg), dami stump length (cm), dami stump width (cm), fruit rind thickness (mm), flake thickness (mm), dami width (cm), sugar content (brix), seed coat thickness (mld), stalk length (cm), total of seeds, number of seeds per kg fruit.

Data Analysis

Field observation data were analyzed using two approaches:

a. Component Analysis

Qualitative data and quantitative data were examined using statistical parameters, including mean values, standard deviations, maximum values, and minimum values.

b. Genetic Diversity Analysis

Morphological observation data from all plant samples were analyzed to assess their similarity levels based on traits such as crown shape, branching pattern, leaf blade shape, leaf apex shape, leaf color, and leaf base shape (Figure 2).

Jackfruit plant in Pasar Manna District, exhibit various morphological characteristics that can be distinguished between the shape, color, and size of their organs. Qualitatively, the crown shape, branching pattern, and variations in the shape of the leaf blade, apex, and base display distinctive diversity. Leaf colour, as well fruit shape, fruit rind colour and pulp flake color, serve as distinguishing factors among plant. Additionally, the seed shape and seed coat colour and the stalk attachment to fruit are important characteristics in identifying differences among jackfruit plants in this region.

Jackfruit plant in Pasar Manna District have measurable quantitative characteristics, such as trunk diameter, leaf blade length and leaf blade width, and fruit including length, width, and diameter. The fruit weight, fruit hardness, wight fresh flake without seed, and seed weight are key indicators of productivity. Other observed factors include dami wight, dami weight and fruit rind per kg, dami stump length and width, fruit rind and flake thickness, and sugar content measured in Brix, which determines sweetness levels. Seed coat thickness, stalk length, and the total and number of seeds per kilogram of fruit are also crucial factors in evaluating jackfruit plants in this area. Understanding these qualitative and quantitative characteristics enables the identification of superior varieties and the selection of plants with the best traits for further cultivation and development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Result

Figure 2. Relationships among jackfruit genotypes based on morphological analysis of crown shape, branching pattern, and leaf characteristics.

The morphological analyzed of jackfruit trees from Pasar Manna district identified significant variation across 35 traits. Crown shape displayed multiple phenotypic variations, including pyramidal, broadly pyramidal, elliptical, and irregular form. Cluster analysis identified two distinct jackfruit similarity group: Group I (PM1, PM2, PB2, PB1, KB2, TM2, and Group II (PS2, PS1, KB1, TM1). A comprehensive summary of both qualitative and quantitative results is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics of Jackfruit Plants in Pasar Manna District, South Bengkulu Based on the Similarity Test of Jackfruit Groups

Characteristics	Group 1	Group 2
Crown shape	Pyramidal-broadly pyramidal	Broadly pyramidal-elliptical-irregular
Branching pattern	Erect-opposite-verticillate	Opposite-verticillate-irregular
Leaf blade shape	Obovate-elliptic	Elliptic
Leaf apex shape	Acuminate	Acuminate
Leaf colour	dark green	dark green
Leaf base shape	Oblique-rounded-cuneate	Oblique-rounded
Fruit shape	Spheroid-ellipsoid	Ellipsoid
Stalk attachment to fruit	Flattened-inflated	Flattened
Flake shape	Spheroid-rectangular-oblong-twisted	Twisted-oblong-cordate
Seed shape	Reniform	Reniform
Fruit rind colour	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow
Pulp flake colour	Light yellow	Light yellow
Seed coat colour	Off white-creamish	Dull brown
Trunk diameter (cm)	44-130 cm	76-110 cm
Leaf blade length (cm)	11.8 -15.3 cm	13.4-15.9 cm
Leaf blade width (cm)	5.8-9.05 cm	8.6-9.3 cm
Fruit length (cm)	40-43 cm	40 cm
Fruit width (cm)	12-23 cm	34 cm
Fruit diameter (cm)	26-68 cm	66 cm
Fruit weight (kg)	7.6-8.9 cm	5.8 cm
Fruit hardness (kgf)	9.74-13.6 kgf	15.0 kgf
Weight fresh flake without seed (g)	152.99-408.77 g	96.49 g
Seed weight (g)	37.49-6893 g	167.02 g
Dami weight and fruit rind per kg (g)	522.3-809.52 g	736.49 g
Dami weight (kg)	4.6-8.3 kg	3.5kg
Dami stump length (cm)	30-31 cm	20 cm
Dami stump width (cm)	7-14 cm	6 cm
Fruit rind thickness (mm)	1.1-1.8 mm	1.5mm
Flake thickness (mm)	0.45-.52 mm	0.45 mm
Dami width (cm)	1 cm	1cm
Sugar content (brix)	11-17 Brix	13 Brix
Seed coat thickness (mld)	0.7 mld	0.7 mld
Stalk length (cm)	6-19 cm	20 cm
Total of seeds	44-52	81
Number of seeds per kg	7-16	21

b. Discussion

Jackfruit exhibits significant morphological diversity due to genetic and environmental factors. The variations in fruit size, flake shape, and sugar content suggest high adaptability to local conditions. Genetic diversity within a population arises from differences in genotype value, which is influenced by introduction, hybridization, mutation, and environmental adaptation. The observed morphological traits, such as fruit rind thickness, flake colour, and seed shape, align with previous studies. The implications of these findings suggest that the local jackfruit population in Pasar Manna District has potential for breeding programs.

Morphological diversity enhances jackfruit adaptability and resilience, supporting efforts to develop superior germplasm for improved cultivation and commercialization. This diversity is likely influenced by factors such as introduction, hybridization, mutation, and possibly transgenic processes. These results are consistent with the findings of [13], who stated that genetic diversity within a population emerges from differences in genotype values among individuals, driven by factors such as introduction, crossing, mutation, and transgenic modifications.

Figure 3. Morphological diversity of crown shape in various jackfruit genotypes. (A): pyramidal, (B): irregular, (C): elliptical, (D): broadly pyramidal, (E): elliptical.

Tree architecture is shaped by the growth patterns of the trunk, branches, and twigs [14]. Jackfruit displays considerable variation in crown shape and branching patterns, which are important architectural traits. This extensive phenotypic variation can be utilized in morphological characterization. According to [15], variations in gene action and interaction, influenced by genetic factors, can result in diverse segregation patterns in jackfruit. This diversity is attributed to the heterozygous nature of F1 parents, leading to offspring with varied characteristics. Furthermore, [16] shows that phenotypic diversity in jackfruit plants is driven by genetic factors, contributing to genotypic diversity, including variations in leaf morphology.

In this study, the shape of the jackfruit leaf blade was observed to be obovate and elliptical, with a dark green color, while the leaf apex shape was acuminate. In contrast, the study by [17] found that jackfruit leaves had an oval shape and were dark green in color. Similarly, [18] reported that jackfruit leaves are oblong in shape and dark green, with an acuminate leaf apex.

Beyond leaf morphology, significant diversity was observed in other jackfruit characteristics. Flake thickness and fruit rind thickness play key roles in determining the number of fruit flakes obtained. According to [2], seeds typically make up 8-15% of the total jackfruit weight. In this study, the dami and rind accounted for 40-50% of the fruit weight. The dami serves as a protective layer for the fruit and supports the flakes during development. The flakes consist of white dami sheets that surround the entire fruit flake (Figure 4).

The maximum fruit rind thickness observed in accession TM2 was 1.8 mm, which is comparable to the 2.08 mm thickness reported by [6] in Mexican jackfruit, suggesting potential variations in fruit flake content across varieties. Additionally, cross-sectional analysis revealed similarities in the density of fruit flakes within the jackfruit (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The thickness of the fruit skin and the cross-sectional shape of the jackfruit were observed to have an influence on the density of fruit flakes within the fruit. A): Tanjung Mulia 1, (B): Tanjung Mulia 2, (C): Padang Sialang 1.

Jackfruit in Pasar Manna District displayed a maximum fruit weight of 8.9 kg, fruit hardness of 15.0 kgf, sugar content of 17 °Brix, and light yellow flakes. These characteristics show variation in weight and quality when compared to other studies. For instance, [19] reported a jackfruit fruit weight of approximately 25 kg, fruit length of 100 cm, and yellowish-green to bright yellow flakes. Meanwhile, in Bihar, India recorded a maximum fruit weight of 44.63 kg, fruit length of 59.54 cm and a sugar content of 15.94 °Brix [11]. In comparison, [20] found that jackfruit in the San Diego market reached a maximum weight of only 35 kg. Besides, Andhra Pradesh showed maximum fruit weight 19.96 kg, and fruit length 55.00 cm [21]. In jackfruit, undeveloped or unpollinated fleshy petals, which are known as dami are found among fleshy petals and may be thick, large, sweet, and edible [3]. In research, dami colour is white and weigh 3.5-8.3 kg with dami width 1 cm.

A notable diversity in jackfruit traits is apparent, particularly in fruit shape and flake color. The jackfruit accessions from Pasar Manna District showed spheroid and ellipsoid shapes (Figure 4). In contrast, [22] reported a broader range of fruit shapes in Meghalaya, India, including ellipsoid, oblong, spheroid, clavate, and irregular forms. However, the fruit rind color exhibited uniformity across the studied accessions, with a greenish-yellow hue.

Figure 5. Fruit shape variations observed in the studied accessions. (A): Tanjung Mulia 1 ellipsoid, (B): Tanjung Mulia 2 ellipsoid, (C): Padang Sialang 1 spheroid.

Furthermore, the color of the jackfruit fruit flakes from the studied accessions was uniformly light yellow (Figure 6). In contrast, [23] observed a broader range of fruit flake colors, including 41% yellow, 31% orange, and 28% white. Figure 6 illustrates the jackfruit fruit flake shape in Tanjung Mulia 1, Tanjung Mulia 2, and Padang Sialang 1 accessions. Jackfruit seeds shape variation exhibited: Tanjung Mulia 1 and Tanjung Mulia 2 reniform, and Padang Sialang 1 irregular (Figure 7). Seed coat color also varied, with off-white observed in Tanjung Mulia 1, creamish in Tanjung Mulia 2, and dull brown in Padang Sialang 1 (Figure 6). Amylum from jackfruit seeds contains positive phytochemical compounds such as flavonoids, saponins, and steroids. [24]

Figure 6. Fruit flake color and shape exhibited variability across the accession samples, with observable differences evident in a left-to-right progression. (A)Tanjung Mulia 1: rectangular, spheroid, oblong, irregular. (B)Tanjung Mulia 2: cordate, twisted, spheroid, oblong. (C)Padang Sialang 1: cordate, oblong, oblong, twisted.

Figure 7. Seed shapes of the sampled accessions are depicted from left to right. (A)Tanjung Mulia 1: reniform, (B)Tanjung Mulia 2: irregular, (C)Padang Sialang 1: reniform.

The morphological diversity observed within the jackfruit population underscores its importance for plant breeding initiatives. According to [16], successful plant breeding largely depends on effective selection, which requires high genetic diversity and heritability within the breeding population. Although breeding perennial crops like jackfruit can be time-consuming, indirect selection methods, such as selecting for specific leaf shapes or adaptability to environmental conditions, can be utilized. [25] emphasized the necessity of establishing nurseries to ensure optimal development of jackfruit plants.

Both morphological and genetic analyses have shown variation in jackfruit within a single interbreeding population. This diversity can be leveraged to develop breeding and conservation strategies aimed at enhancing jackfruit production and, consequently, increasing farmers' incomes. However, relying solely on morphology for germplasm selection may be misleading, highlighting the need for an integrated approach that considers both morphological and genetic factors in breeding programs [26].

CONCLUSION

This study conforms significant genetic diversity in jackfruit population in Pasar Manna District, Bengkulu, Indonesia based on morphological traits. Qualitative traits of jackfruit include crown shape, leaf, fruit, flake, seed and quantitative traits variations were noted in trunk diameter, with the longest being 130 cm, leaf length at 17.1 cm, leaf width at 9.3 cm, and the highest sugar content, at 17 °Brix. Cluster analysis identified 2 major jackfruit group distinguished by variation in crown shape, leaf characteristic, fruit morphological, and seed traits. These findings contribute to the selection of superior jackfruit varieties for conservation and breeding programs. Future research incorporating molecular markers could further validate these morphological classifications.

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